

Reactions of IR varieties to *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens* in the seedbox screening test, IRRI, 1983-84.

Variety	Damage rating ^a			
	<i>N. nigropictus</i>		<i>N. virescens</i>	
IR5	6.3	de	7.0	def
IR8	5.7	cde	6.3	cde
IR20	6.3	de	7.0	def
IR22	5.0	bcde	8.3	ef
IR24	4.3	bcd	4.3	abc
IR26	3.7	bc	5.7	bcd
IR28	3.0	b	3.7	ab
IR29	3.0	b	3.0	a
IR30	3.7	bc	3.0	a
IR32	4.3	bcd	6.3	cde
IR34	4.3	bcd	4.3	abc
IR36	3.0	b	6.3	cde
IR38	4.3	bcd	5.7	bcd
IR40	5.0	bcde	5.7	bcd
IR42	4.3	bcd	7.0	def
IR43	3.7	bc	4.3	abc
IR44	4.3	bcd	4.3	abc
IR45	4.3	bcd	5.7	bcd
IR46	5.7	cde	6.3	cde
IR48	5.0	bcde	7.0	def
IR50	4.3	bcd	3.7	ab
IR52	4.3	bcd	3.7	ab
IR54	4.3	bcd	3.7	ab
IR56	3.0	b	3.0	a
IR58	3.0	b	3.7	ab
IR60	3.0	b	3.0	a
Nira (susceptible check)	9.0	e	9.0	f

^a Av of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test. The damage rating is based on the 1980 SES 0-9 scale.

those to *N. virescens*. Twelve varieties had similar reactions to both species (see table). IR56, IR58, and IR60 are highly resistant to both *N. nigropictus* and *N. virescens*. They also have resistance to brown planthopper. □

Screening wild rices for resistance to green leafhopper (GLH)

Q. M. A. Razzaque and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

We screened 91 wild rices for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Stål) and *N. virescens* (Distant) using the seedbox test in the greenhouse. Separate seedboxes were used for each GLH species. Test entries were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with resistant IR29 and susceptible Nira. Each seedbox was a

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Species	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Damage rating ^a	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica	100168	1.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100172	1.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Japan	100179	1.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaya	100180	1.7	2.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Burma	100181	1.0	1.7
<i>O. sativa/O. rufipogon</i>	India	100183	2.0	4.3
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Taiwan, China	100820	0.7	0.7
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Taiwan, China	100821	3.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100883	1.0	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100885	1.0	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	India	100887	1.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100890	1.7	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100891	1.7	1.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	India	100892	5.7	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	USA	100895	1.7	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Thailand	100896	1.0	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Mexico	100914	1.0	0.7
<i>O. sativa/O. nivara</i>	Cambodia	100917	1.7	3.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	100937	1.0	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100947	3.0	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100948	1.0	2.3
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	100953	1.0	2.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	100956	1.0	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Mexico	100959	3.7	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100962	3.7	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100963	1.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	100964	3.7	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica	100965	5.0	0.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Panama	100966	1.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	100973	3.7	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101073	3.7	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101074	3.0	2.3
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101077	5.7	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101078	5.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101081	4.3	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101082	5.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101084	5.7	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101086	5.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101089	5.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101094	6.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101096	3.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101097	0.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101099	3.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101100	3.7	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101101	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101112	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101113	5.7	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101114	4.3	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101115	1.3	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101117	6.3	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101118	5.7	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101121	7.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101122	3.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101123	4.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101124	3.0	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101125	5.7	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101126	4.3	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101128	5.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101129	5.7	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101132	3.0	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101133	5.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101137	3.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101139	3.0	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101141	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101142	5.7	0.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	101143	1.3	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101149	3.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101150	1.3	0.7

Cont'd

Species	Origin	IRRI acc. no.	Damage rating ^a	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101152	4.3	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101154	5.0	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	101155	4.3	1.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	101166	5.7	1.0
<i>O. punctata</i>	Tanzania	101171	6.3	1.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	Nigeria	101329	7.0	1.7
<i>O. minuta</i>	Japan	101386	7.7	3.3
<i>O. minuta</i>	Japan	101387	7.7	1.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Guatemala	101392	1.3	1.0
<i>O. alta</i>	USA	101395	3.0	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Vietnam	101399	5.0	1.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	101408	5.0	1.0
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	101409	3.7	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	101412	4.3	1.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	India	101414	4.3	1.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	Kenya	101417	4.3	0.7
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Uganda	101422	5.7	1.7
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Uganda	101426	4.3	1.7
<i>O. punctata</i>	Tanzania	101434	3.0	1.3
<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	101439	5.0	1.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Mexico	101443	0.3	0.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Indonesia	102382	3.7	1.3
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Nicaragua	102481	0.3	1.0
<i>O. sativa</i> (Nira)	India	1748 (susceptible check)	9.0	9.0
<i>O. sativa</i> (IR29)	Philippines	30414 (resistant check)	3.7	3.7

^a Av of 3 replications. Damage rating is based on 0-9 scale.

replication. At 10-15 d after seeding, seedlings were infested with 4-5 3d-instar GLH nymphs per seedling. When Nira seedlings died, test entries were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale. Each entry was replicated three times.

N. nigropictus is more virulent and caused more damage to wild rices than *N. virescens*. Of the 91 wild rices, 53 (59%) were resistant (score 0-3.9), 31 (33%) were moderately resistant (score 4.0-5.9), and 7 (8%) were susceptible (score 6.0-9) to *N. nigropictus* (see table). All but one of the wild rices were resistant to *N. virescens*.

When the IR varieties (*Oryza sativa*) were screened for GLH resistance in another test, *N. virescens* was generally more virulent. Also, the weed *Leersia hexandra* was a better host for *N. nigropictus* than for *N. virescens*. Thus, *N. nigropictus* is better adapted to feeding on wild rices and *L. hexandra* than on cultivated rice. □

Screening for green leafhopper (GLH) resistance

Q. M. A. Razzaque and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

We screened 18 rices with genes for resistance to *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) for resistance to *N. nigropictus* (Stål) and *N. virescens* using the seedbox screening test. Test entries were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes with IR29 as the resistant check and Nira as the susceptible check. Separate seedboxes were used for each hopper species. Seven days after seeding (DAS), seedlings were thinned to 15-20 per entry and infested with 4-5 3d-instar nymphs per seedling of each species. When all susceptible check seedlings died, entries were rated for damage using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

All the rices with genes for *N. virescens* resistance were resistant (rating of 3-3.7) or moderately resistant (rating 4.3-5.7) to *N. nigropictus*. Jhingasail, Lien-tsan 50,

Reaction of rice cultivars with genes for *N. virescens* resistance when infested with *N. nigropictus* or *N. virescens* in the seedbox screening test, IRRI, 1983-84.

Variety	Origin	Gene	Damage rating ^a	
			<i>N. nigropictus</i>	<i>N. virescens</i>
Pankhari 203	India	<i>Glh</i> 1	3.0 bc	3.3 ab
Jhingasail	Bangladesh	<i>Glh</i> 2	3.0 bc	3.7 bc
Lien-tsan-50	China	<i>Glh</i> 2	3.0 bc	3.7 bc
ASD7	India	<i>Glh</i> 2	4.3 cde	3.7 bc
Godalki	Bangladesh	<i>Glh</i> 2	5.7 ef	5.0 bcd
Palasithari 601	Sri Lanka	<i>Glh</i> 2	5.0 def	3.0 a
H5	Sri Lanka	<i>Glh</i> 3	2.3 bc	6.3 cd
DNJ 97	Bangladesh	<i>Glh</i> 3	4.3 cde	3.7 bc
IR8	Philippines	<i>Glh</i> 3	5.7 ef	5.7 bcde
Arai	Bangladesh	<i>Glh</i> 3	3.7 cd	3.7 bc
IR30	Philippines	<i>Glh</i> 3	3.0 bc	3.0 a
Ptb 8	India	<i>glh</i> 4	3.7 cd	5.7 bcde
IR42	Philippines	<i>glh</i> 4	3.7 cd	7.0 cde
ASD8	India	<i>Glh</i> 5	5.0 def	3.0 a
IR36	Philippines	<i>Glh</i> 6	3.0 bc	7.0 cde
Ptb 18	India	<i>Glh</i> 6	4.3 cde	5.7 bcde
TAPL #796	Bangladesh	<i>Glh</i> 6	1.7 a	3.7 bc
Moddai Karuppan	Sri Lanka	<i>Glh</i> 7	3.0 bc	5.7 bcde
IR29 (resistant check)	Philippines	—	3.0 bc	3.7 bc
Nira (susceptible check)	India	—	9.0 f	9.0 e

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Damage rating is based on a 0-9 scale. Av of 3 replications.

Arai, IR30, and TAPL #796 were resistant and six rices were moderately resistant to both hopper species (see table). In general,

reactions to both species were similar, except for IR36 and IR42, which had higher damage when infested with *N. virescens*. □